

Structural optimization of Fused Filament Fabricated components with nature inspired biomechanical optimization methods

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Abstract

Additive manufacturing processes have evolved from rapid prototyping to the production of directly usable components. Extrusion-based processes such as Fused Filament Fabrication (FFF) enable fast and, for smaller quantities, cost-effective productions. FFF can create complex geometries, by extruding filament strands layer by layer. A limitation of this technology is the low mechanical strength due to the layered structure. Print strands result in orthotropic properties, with strength and stiffness highest along print directions and decreasing in deviating directions. In order to design highly robust components without over dimensioning, it is not only necessary to take the anisotropy through the layered structure and the printing patterns into account, but also to optimize the printing paths themselves.

Computer Aided Internal Optimization (CAIO) is a method inspired by tree growth that aims at optimizing the internal structure of materials. Based on the Finite Element Method (FEM), CAIO iteratively rotates the orthotropic axis of each finite element in local principal normal stress directions and thus aligns the directions of maximum material strength and maximum load. For the example of a perforated plate subjected to a unidirectional tensile load, a FEM analysis was performed. The local orthotropy orientation, calculated by CAIO was translated into printing paths and demonstrators were fabricated in PLA using an FFF printer. Applying this optimization and compared to industry-standard printing patterns with the same amount of

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printed material, an increase in tensile strength of up to 28% was realized. In addition, the Soft Kill Method (SKO) was used to optimize the topology. The SKO method aims to optimize components for maximum stiffness and strength while minimizing material usage and thus component mass. The method is based on the biomechanical principles found in bone growth, where mineralization and demineralization controlled by mechanical stress vary structure and stiffness. By applying SKO to the FFF printed parts, a reduction in weight of 25% was realized. Even though the material usage was reduced, an increase in tensile strength of 5%, compared to industry standard prints, was achieved. Compared to standard patterned specimen of the same mass, an increase in breaking load of almost 70% was accomplished. The results of both methods show significant improvement in tensile strength of Fused Filament Fabricated parts. This suggests a strong potential for applying CAIO and SKO in optimized manufacturing of highly robust components.

Keywords: Additive Manufacturing, Fused Filament Fabrication, biomimetic structural optimization, Computer Aided Internal Optimization, Soft Kill Option

1 Introduction

Fused Filament Fabrication (FFF), also known as Fused Deposition Modeling (FDM), is a widely used 3D printing technique that offers much more design freedom of printable parts compared to classic manufacturing processes. This additive manufacturing process is based on layer-by-layer deposition of material to create three-dimensional objects. FFF has gained popularity due to its low initial investment, wide range of applications, and ease of use [1]. The flexibility in printable geometry is one of the key advantages of FFF. This technology allows the creation of complex structures, including complex internal geometries and customized designs. The ability to produce parts with varying infill patterns and densities further enhances the versatility of FFF in creating objects with specific mechanical properties [2]. Despite its geometric flexibility, FFF-produced parts often suffer from weak mechanical strength compared to traditionally manufactured components. This limitation is primarily attributed to the printing path orientation and layered structure [3], which results in local orthotropic material properties [4], [5]. The greatest tensile strength is achieved when a uniaxial printed sample is loaded in the direction of the printing strands. Furthermore, upright printed samples have the lowest shear strength [6]. This can be attributed to weak adhesion between the applied layers [7]. The stiffness and tensile strength are directly linked to the infill degree of the specimen, i.e. the ratio between strength and mass [2]. Typically, more material and denser infill patterns lead to increased strength [8]. The orthotropic material properties in terms of tensile strength of FFF 3D printed Polylactic acid (PLA) are comparable to fiber-reinforced polymers [9]. Both materials have highest strength in the direction of the printing paths or fiber orientation [6], [10].

The optimization of 3D printing parameters is crucial for producing highly robust parts with minimal defects [11]. While many studies focus on interdependent parameters such as infill density, layer height, print speed, and extrusion temperature, these optimizations have limitations in addressing stress concentrations and notch effects inherent to component

geometry. This necessitates the incorporation of structural optimization techniques to further enhance component strength. The potential for optimization lies in the stress-optimized infill layout of 3D printed components, whereby the structure of the components is adapted to the load during use [12]. Optimized printing paths and material distributions can reduce the amount of printed material and thus also the production time [13] and creating components with high load bearing capacity [2].

This manuscript examines how biomechanic optimization can increase tensile strength of FFF components. Like FFF 3D printed materials and fiber-reinforced polymers, many naturally grown biological materials, such as wood, have orthotropic material properties[14]. Trees react to stress through adaptive growth and orient fibers in the direction of the force flow according to their greatest load-bearing capacity [15]. Bone growth is also adaptive to stress. Bones accumulate more material in high stressed areas and remove it via demineralization processes in less stressed regions [16] [17]. Taking these mechanisms into account, and with use of the Finite Element Method (FEM) structural optimization of technical components according to biological growth principles is facilitated. Soft Kill Option (SKO) and Computer Aided Internal Optimization (CAIO) create optimized structural designs based on Finite Element Analyses [18]. CAIO was originally developed to locally align fiber orientation along the principal stresses in fiber-reinforced composites. The orientation of the fibers along the force flow increases the load-bearing capacity and stiffness of the composites significantly [19]. CAIO is used in this work to adapt the printing path orientation to the stress and to increase the tensile strength of the structure. As an example, the stress distribution in a tensile loaded plate with a hole is investigated in more detail in this work. First, the orientation of the main stress trajectories are determined using the finite element method and subsequent CAIO optimization in order to determine the printing paths for additive manufacturing. In addition to the flexibility of the FFF in terms of printable geometries, the lightweight potential is a key advantage of the manufacturing process. In order to create a lightweight yet strong component the perforated

tensile specimen is adapted using SKO. It is a topology optimization in which areas with high load are maintained and lower loaded areas are only filled with a low infill density. In order to compare the tensile strength of the two optimized specimen types to industry standard prints, a set of reference specimens with different standard printing patterns was printed and tested.

2 Experimental

2.1 Sample geometry

Here, the influence of structural adaptation of printing patterns in FFF 3D printed components under tensile load was investigated, using the example of a flat, perforated tensile specimen based on DIN EN ISO 527 [20], shown in Figure 1. The perforated plate is a simple and representative geometry, which is common in actual component layout. Therefore it is a suitable example to test the applicability of optimization methods. The height of the specimen is 3 mm and the hole has a diameter of 5 mm. The width is 15 mm and the length of the testing zone is 50 mm and 140 mm of the total specimens.

Figure 1: Shape of perforated tensile specimen based on DIN EN ISO 527 with clamping and testing zones. This is a representative geometry as it is commonly used in component design.

2.2 FEM simulation CAIO

A two dimensional geometry model of the perforated plate was created in ANSYS MAPDL (Ansys, USA). Initially, the orthotropy axis were oriented in direction of the global coordinate system. The high stiffness E_1 is directed in x direction. Due to the different stiffness of additively manufactured samples parallel and perpendicular to the printing path [8], an

anisotropy in stiffness of 10% was assumed in the model. Because of symmetry of the perforated plate, just a quarter was modelled and later the entire sample put together by mirroring the results. After generating the model's geometry, a mesh with four-node elements was created. Areas experiencing high loads and stress gradients were meshed more densely. After setting boundary conditions and applying a tensile load, the stress state was calculated. For the FEM analysis a plane stress and strain state was assumed. This assumption is sufficient, because the perforated plate has a uniform thickness, which is less than the cross section dimension and is in-plane loaded [21]. CAIO is used with ANSYS MAPDL (Ansys, USA). After a FE analysis it determines the angle between global coordinate system and the principal stress direction in each element. The CAIO method rotates the orthotropic axis with the greatest stiffness in the direction of the force flow, i.e. in the direction of the 1st principal stress. As the local orthotropy axis is rotated, the material properties change and so does the force flow. With the change of material properties, a new FE analysis must be performed to determine the new stress state. The CAIO calculation and the FE analysis were repeated until no significant change in the rotation angle could be determined [22]. Figure 2 shows the iterative process of the CAIO method.

Figure 2: Flow chart of CAIO method, which rotates the orthotropic axes in direction auf the principal stress trajectories.

2.3 FEM Simulation SKO

The SKO method (Soft Kill Option) is a topology optimization method for lightweight construction applications and aims to optimize components for maximum stiffness and strength while minimizing material usage [15]. The method varies the stiffness, modelled as Young's modulus, in a structure, increasing stiffness of elements that carry more load and weakening elements that carry less load [23]. This optimization approach is based on the natural model of bone growth. The mineralisation or demineralisation is controlled by mechanical load [16]. As mechanical stress increases, bone material is deposited in greater quantities and locally making the bone stiffer. In contrast, areas subjected to lower loads undergo bone resorption, leading to a reduction in bone mass [24] [16].

Figure 3: Flow chart of SKO method shows iterative optimization process, where high loaded are getting assigned to a higher stiffness and lower stressed areas getting less stiff.

As illustrated in Figure 3, the SKO method starts with a FEM analysis to determine the stress distribution for the anticipated load scenario of the component. It is essential that the model geometry includes the optimized shape entirety. First, a constant stiffness, set as Young's modulus, is assumed over the entire geometry in the simulation. The stiffness is then varied depending on the locally occurring stress and the stress distribution is recalculated for the same load but with a locally varied Young's modulus. These iterations are repeated until a clear

distinction between areas with a high and low stiffness can be recognized [23]. The variation of the Young's modulus is incremental and is defined as a function of temperature for each element. The temperature is chosen as the control variable because it makes SKO easy to adapt to any FEM programme, as these all contain temperature-dependent elasticity. Areas with a maximum set temperature are assigned the maximum Young's modulus, while below a certain temperature the minimum Young's modulus is assigned, with a linear relationship in between [25]. With each iteration, a new temperature is assigned to each element based on the difference between the calculated and reference stress and an adjustment parameter b . The parameter b , between 0 and 1, controls the adjustment speed.

$$E_{n+1} = E_n + b (\sigma_n - \sigma_{ref})$$

The reference stress σ_{ref} is a predefined value that is valid for the entire volume. Optimization is most effective if the reference stress is initially set to a small value and then gradually increased. The higher the reference stress is set, the more material is removed [23].

2.4 Translating CAIO optimization into G code

To transfer the CAIO optimization into the printed part, the G Code was adapted to the simulation results. Therefore the printing path follows the principal stress trajectories. When the printing paths are orientated along the principal stress direction, they are oriented along the force flow and thus in the direction of their greatest load capacity [26]. The rotation angles of orthotropic axis resulting from the optimization were used to extract the path coordinates, following the trajectories. The coordinates along the principal stress trajectories were read from ANSYS MAPDL (Ansys, USA). The modelling was done on a quarter model; the coordinates were mirrored in order to generate a path over the entire length of the sample. The starting points of the path coordinates were located at the narrowest point of the model, where the stress concentration caused by the hole is greatest. They were placed with the distance of a strand width. The coordinates were subsequently extracted along the principal stress trajectories from

the model and exported as a text file. The text file was converted to G Code by a self-written python script.

The G-code is based on several standard commands, each beginning with the letter G or M. The G0 and G1 commands correspond to a linear movement between printhead and platform to a defined location with a given speed. G0 is a command for fast machine movements without extruding material. The G1 command uses in addition to the coordinates of the extruder movement a fourth dimension E. The E value defines the cumulative amount of the filament that is fed through the nozzle [27]. A typical command has the following form:

G1 X10 Y20 Z0.2 E5 F1200

In this example, the printhead moves to the position $x = 10$ mm and $y = 20$ mm, at a height of $z = 0.2$ mm, with a speed of 1200 mm/s and extrudes filament. The extrusion quantity is determined by multiplying the cross-section of the extruded material by the length of the section to be extruded [28]. In the area where the sample geometry widens behind the hole, the paths are separated by gaps. If the gaps are of sufficient size, a new path was inserted. Low stressed areas were not optimized and were filled with a standardized, crossed line pattern with a grid angle of $\pm 45^\circ$, generated by the slicing software UlitMaker Cura (UltiMaker, Netherlands).

Since the optimization is limited to the printing plane, the printing commands are repeated in each layer, up to the specimen high of 3 mm. While the middle part of the specimen was printed according to optimization results, the clamping zone was filled with a standard cross line pattern, generated by the slicing software UlitMaker Cura.

2.5 G Code synthesis for SKO optimized structure

The result of the SKO optimization is a component that primarily consists of structural elements subjected to tensile stress. In order to transfer the SKO optimization to the printed component, the tested area of the specimen was divided into two zones in the slicer: the stiffness in areas with low stress from the SKO optimization was reduced by decreasing the filling density down

to 20%, while areas subjected to high load were set to 100% infill density. In areas with 100% filling density, a line pattern was selected in the tensile direction and a grid pattern in the less dense filled areas.

2.6 G Code synthesis of reference specimens

The production workflow of standard and optimized specimen differs in creating the model and further generating the machine code for the 3D printer. The manufacturing process of the reference specimens starts with modelling the part geometry and creating a 3D volume model in the CAD software Autodesk Fusion 360 version 2.0 (Autodesk, USA). The link between volume model and the printer is the slicing software that generates the G Code [29]. Printing parameters such as layer thickness and temperatures were defined there and are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: printing parameters of slicer generated G code

Parameter	
Extrusion temperature	205 °C
Built plate temperature	60 °C
Layer height	0.2 mm
Strand width	0.42 mm

There are a large number of pre-set standard patterns in the slicer that can be used to fill printed parts. Common structures are lines or grid patterns, which were varied in size and infill density [30]. Four types of specimens were designed for reference, illustrated in Figure 4:

1. Layer-by-layer alternating +/- 45° line pattern, with 100% infill density.
2. Longitudinal line pattern, also at 100% infill density.
3. Alternating longitudinal and transverse (0°/90°) strands, 100% infill density.
4. Longitudinal line pattern, but with a reduced infill density of 75%.

The G code for the reference specimens was generated with the slicing software UlitMaker Cura.

Figure 4: Three standard patterns used for reference specimens. a) layer-by-layer alternating $\pm 45^\circ$ line pattern, b) alternating longitudinal and transverse ($0^\circ/90^\circ$) strands, c) longitudinal line pattern

2.7 Printing

Poly lactide acid (PLA) is most commonly used as a FFF filament material due to its good availability, low cost, non-toxicity, flexibility and fast printability and was therefore used for the samples tested here [1]. All specimens were printed with a standard Creality Ender 5 S1 printer (Creality, China) and the same filament batch and general setup. In order to compare and quantify the load bearing capacity of all specimens, five samples of each type were printed. A scheme of the FFF 3D printing is shown in Figure 5. A filament wire is melted by a hotend in the printhead and applied to a heated printing bed via a nozzle [31]. The filament is pushed through the nozzle by a direct extruder. The overall geometry is created layer by layer, with each layer formed of a pattern of individual printing strands [32].

Figure 5: Scheme of 3D printing by Fused Filament Fabrication: melted filament is extruded layer by layer through a nozzle on a printing bed. There the layered structure is realized by lowering the printing platform for every new applied layer, but can also be realized by moving the nozzle upwards.

2.8 Sample characterization and tensile test

The weight of each sample was measured with a precision scale to one milligram. In order to investigate the effect of the optimized filling patterns, all samples were subjected to a tensile test using a universal testing machine. The Instron 1185 tensile testing machine (Instron GmbH, USA) used consists of a stationary and a movable crosshead, which was moved at a constant speed of 2 mm/min. During the tests, the deformation of the specimens over the movement of the crosshead was measured with an inductive displacement transducer and the applied force was measured with a load cell. The data was simultaneously recorded and displayed on a monitor using the DASYLab32 software (National Instruments, USA).

3 Results

3.1 FEM results for the CAIO Method and G code

The FEM analysis determines the principle stress distribution, as seen in Figure 6. The notch effect of the perforation creates a stress concentration at the rim of the hole.

Figure 6: Meshed model (center) with the initially set orientation of the orthotropy axis in direction of the global coordinate system (left) and the associated first principal stress distribution (right)

CAIO method determines the rotation angle between the principal stress direction and the global coordinate system for each element. The rotation of the local orthotropy axis changes the material properties and thus also the force flow and stress field, displayed in Figure 7. After the first CAIO calculation, a new FEM analysis was carried out to determine the new stress state. The stress concentration at the edge of the perforation increases after the CAIO calculation, which seems contradictory. However, since a low stiffness in the direction of the tensile load was initially defined in the model, the stress concentration at the edge of the hole is lower, and so is the strength. Due to the rotation of the orthotropic axis, the stress concentration at the notch increases. With the orientation of the printing paths along the principle stress direction, the tensile strength of the printed specimen is expected to increase. The CAIO method converges quickly, as the number of iterations increases, the course of the principal stress trajectories, as well as the stress state, hardly changes [20]. For the perforated plate the CAIO analysis was iterated only two times.

Initial state

Iteration 1

Iteration2

Figure 7: Iterations of CAIO method as it rotates the orthotropic axis of every element. This changes the material properties and thus the stress distribution of the next iteration. In the initial state (a) all elements have orthotropic axis in direction of the coordinate system, creating a highly stressed area next to the hole through a notch effect (b). The principle stress vectors are shown for each element (c). In the first iteration, the orthotropic axis are rotated in the direction of the principle stress (a). As the stress field changes (b), the orientation of the principle stress is also changing (c). In the second iteration the rotation of orthotropic axis in direction of new calculated principle stress is repeated

The result of the CAIO is the orientation of the orthotropic axis in every element in the model. By extracting the coordinates of the principal stress trajectories, paths are extracted, as shown in Figure 8. A Python script fills the gaps between the paths. The rim of the specimen is filled with vertical paths and the low stressed area(s) are filled with a $\pm 45^\circ$ altering line patterns.

Figure 8: Generating printing paths based on the CAIO results: a) generation of the printing paths along the principal stress trajectories; b) filling of gaps between the paths; c) principle stress direction in the edge area barely deviates from the vertical direction; d) weakly stressed areas filled with standard filling pattern $\pm 45^\circ$

3.2 FEM result of SKO and transfer to infill pattern

The SKO optimization applied aims reduction of material consumption by adjusting the infill quantity and the print pattern. The same FEM geometry model as in the CAIO optimization was used and mirrored, to get a full model. After defining boundary conditions and load, the stress field was calculated. At the beginning a constant Young's modulus was assigned over the entire geometry and then varied depending on the locally occurring stress. The stress distribution was recalculated for the same load but with a locally varied Young's modulus. These iterations were repeated until a clear distinction between areas with a high and low stiffness were recognizable. Parts of the structure that are subject to low loads have low stiffness and were later filled with low density in the final design of the component [23]. With each iteration, The SKO method assigns a new stiffness to each element based on the difference between the calculated and reference stress and an adjustment parameter b . The parameter b , set to 1, controls the adjustment speed. In Figure 9 the distribution of Young's Modulus calculated with differently set reference stress is shown. The calculated stress σ_n is the stress in each element after each iteration [15], whereby the highest principle stress was calculated here.

σ_{ref} : reference stress

σ_{n} : calculated stress

Display of Young's Modulus distribution

Figure 9: The variation of the Young's modulus (red: high, blue: low) depends on the chosen reference stress. The higher the reference stress is set, the more material is removed

In order to transfer the optimization result into a printing layout, the stiffness of the areas is varied by infill density. The outer geometry of the perforated plate specimen must remain unchanged. When choosing a low reference stress, like 5 or 7 MPa, the resulting structure elements are not rod shaped tensile loaded elements. At a higher reference stress the resulting structure gets slimmer. The application of the 11 MPa result change the outline of the geometry. Since this is to be retained, contour lines are necessary, what makes the structure denser and therefore stiffer and thus blur the results of the optimized internal structure. In this work the result with a reference stress of 10MPa was chosen. It results in a structure with uniform shaped elements with high and low stiffness. It leaves enough material, to keep the outline intact. Figure 10 shows the emerging infill layout. In order to transfer the optimization result to a printed path, the areas are filled with different levels of infill density and the suitable pattern. This results in an overall material reduction of 25%.

Figure 10: result of SKO Method (left) divides the model in clearly separated areas of high or low stiffness. In order to transfer the optimization result to a printed path, the areas are filled with different levels of infill density and the suitable pattern (right). Here the 100% filled areas have a line pattern, because they are loaded tensile. The grid pattern was chosen, as a standard pattern for less dense structures

3.3 Printing results

Figure 12 shows reference samples, next to the CAIO optimized sample. The three standard filled specimens, filled with 100% infill density are used for comparison to the CAIO optimization, shown in Figure 11: variant A with a layer-by-layer alternating $\pm 45^\circ$ line pattern, variant B with a longitudinal line pattern and variant C with alternating longitudinal and transverse ($0^\circ/90^\circ$) strands. A set of five samples were printed of every specimen variant.

Figure 11: example of standard printing patterns: a) $\pm 45^\circ$ line pattern, b) longitudinal lines (0°) and c) alternating longitudinal and transverse ($0^\circ/90^\circ$) line pattern

Figure 12: tested samples: a) CAIO optimized; b) +/- 45° line pattern; c) longitudinal lines (0°); d) alternating longitudinal and transverse (0°/90°) line pattern

Figure 13 shows the printing results of the reference samples, next to SKO optimized sample. Completely filled and 75% filled specimens were used as reference. In the 75% filled specimen, the amount of material used corresponds to the SKO optimized specimen. The reference specimens are filled with a standard line pattern in direction of tensile load. The 100% filled samples are the same samples as the reference of type B used for CAIO comparison.

Figure 13: a) SKO optimized sample; b) 100% filled; c) 75% filled reference sample

3.4 Tensile test results of CAIO optimized samples

In order to compare the amount of printed material among the specimens, the samples were weighted and compared with the calculated mass. The theoretical extruded material is calculated using the quantity of extruded material, defined in the G Code. With a wire thickness of 1.75 mm, the mass can be calculated using the cross-sectional area of the wire, the wire length and the density of PLA (1.2 g/cm³). Table 2 presents the calculated masses of all specimens, the measured mass, and the corresponding standard deviations. Five samples of all four specimen variants were weighted. The theoretical and average weighted total mass of the samples matched with a difference of less than 0.5%.

Table 2: average weighted and calculated mass of all tested specimens

Type	Weighted mass and standard deviation [g]	Theoretically calculated mass [g]	Theoretically mass without reinforcement layer [g]
CAIO	10.903 (0.037)	10.899	9.032
Type A	8.980 (0.018)	9.021	9.021
Type B	10.881 (0.021)	10.831	8.989
Type C	9.006 (0.017)	8.984	8.984

On all five samples of every specimen a tensile test was conducted. Shown in Figure 14 a), all tested samples broke next to the hole. Chipping was observed in all tested CAIO samples. Referring to Figure 14 b), the CAIO optimization increased the breaking load of the optimized samples by 10 to 28%, compared to conventionally generated FFF prints with the same amount of material. The CAIO optimized samples achieved an average breaking load of 1681 N and a standard deviation of 39 N. Specimen B failed at an average breaking load of 1530 N and standard deviation of 6 N, while the samples of specimen A and C had breaking loads of 1351 N and 1312 N with standard deviation of 43 N and 13 N.

a)

b)

Figure 14: Samples after tensile testing and their average breaking load. Left to right: CAIO, +/-45°, 0° and 0°/90°. The average braking load of after CAIO optimization increases by 10 to 28%

3.5 Tensile test results of SKO optimized samples

Figure 15 a) shows an example of every specimen for SKO and the reference specimens and b) the associated average breaking loads. With non-optimized specimens, an increase in breaking load is observed with increasing filling density: From an average of 952 N and standard deviation of 13 N at 75% infill density to 1530 N and standard deviation of 6 N at 100% infill density, which equals an increase by a factor of 1.6. These tensile tests revealed that the SKO optimized samples did not fail at the hole, in contrast to all other samples. The SKO optimized samples fail close to the transition of testing to clamping zone. The optimized specimens had an average breaking load of 1613 N with standard deviation of 21 N. With the same amount of material, meaning a 75% infill density, the average breaking load of the optimized specimen was almost 70% higher than the non-optimized. The SKO optimized specimen showed a 5% higher average breaking load compared to the 100% filled reference specimen, despite a 25% reduction of material.

a)

b)

Figure 15: a) Samples after tensile testing and their average breaking load. Left to right: SKO, reference sample with 100% and 75% infill density. b) associated average breaking loads and standard deviations

4 Discussion

Based on the assumption that the print path orientation in FFF 3D printed components has a similar influence on the load-bearing capacity as the fiber orientation in fiber-reinforced materials [9], printing paths and so the structural properties were adapted to the stress in the component, by orienting the printing paths in direction of principal stress trajectories. Numerous FE-analyses have demonstrated the potential of various optimisation methods [33] [34] [35]. In practice, however, there are inevitably deviations between the modelled and the manufactured component, which affect the success of the optimisation. For example, when optimising the local material orientation, the optimum direction can be determined at any location, starting from any point. The material orientation can be represented using streamlines and implemented as a single printing path in the component. The distance between two neighbouring streamlines can change considerably in the model, but the width of a printed strand can only change to a very small extent. This can easily result in gaps or excess material

between printed strands, which should be avoided as far as possible using suitable strategies. In this work, the optimisation potential and practical feasibility were verified experimentally. The CAIO optimized samples exhibited a higher braking load than the reference specimen. Compared to the specimen with altering line pattern of 0° and 90° , an increase in breaking load of up to 28% was achieved. Compared to the longitudinal printing paths, which is a form of pre-optimization as the printing direction aligns with the load direction, the CAIO optimized samples show an increase in breaking load of 10%, even though the orientation of the printing path is mostly similar in both specimen. The discrepancies in weight within the test area between the clamping zones of all specimen are minimal and can be neglected. The difference in the total weight of the optimized and reference specimens is attributed to the reinforcement layers in the clamping areas for some specimens. Consequently, the improvement in tensile strength is realized by adjusting the printing path orientation in particularly stressed areas with constant material usage. The samples were made from PLA. Usage of other materials would lead to, quantitatively different breaking loads. But as the anisotropy is largely caused by the manufacturing process, comparable qualitative results can be expected.

The SKO optimized specimens show an increase in breaking load of about 5% compared to the standard filled specimen with 100% infill density, while at the same time their mass could be reduced by another 25%. An even more significant increase in breaking load of almost 70% was realized compared to specimen of the same weight. The load case under consideration in this study, stresses the rim areas of the SKO optimized specimens with tension. The printing paths therefore run there in the direction of loading. Due to the adapted structure, the stress distribution in the SKO samples is more homogeneous than in the reference ones. The notch effect around the hole is reduced. Despite a reduced mass, this leads to an increase in tensile strength of 5% compared to completely filled samples. It is noteworthy that the SKO-optimized specimens broke at the transition zone from the clamping to the tested area and not at the hole.

This underlines the reduction of notch effect of the hole by optimization, so the notch effect at the transition zone became critical to failure.

Guidetti et al. (2024) introduced a novel swarm-based approach for generating stress-aligned print trajectories with controlled line spacing [36]. This method uses stress aligned trajectories, following the stress flow based on isotropic material properties [37]. In contrast, the CAIO approach considers changes in stress flow by aligning orthotropic axes to the local principle stresses which leads to slightly different printing paths and a higher load capacity can be expected.

The manual extraction of print trajectories from ANSYS for complex geometries is a limitation of our current approach that requires a more automated solution in the future so that CAIO and SKO can be implemented at scale. While this work primarily examined tensile strength, future research will focus on more complex load scenarios, including alternating loads, to provide a more comprehensive understanding of optimized 3D printed components.

5 Conclusions

Our results demonstrates the transferability of nature-inspired optimization techniques - CAIO and SKO - to FFF 3D printing. The optimization, offers tools to adapt the inner structure of components to the loading conditions. By focusing the optimization on highly loaded areas that are found to be critical to failure before optimization, our approach provides an efficient method for enhancing component strength and lightweight 3D printing.

The following conclusions can be drawn:

- Print paths following optimized trajectories increase tensile strength from at least 10% up to 28%, compared to standard printing patterns.

- The reduction of notch effects is achieved by adapting infill density, thereby tailoring the remaining infill to the load case.
- Concentrating optimization efforts on highly stressed areas helps limit the complexity and effort of the optimization while effectively improving component performance.

Acknowledgements

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Competing Interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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